

“TRENDS IN SHRINKAGE BEHAVIOUR OF BAMBOO POLES TREATED WITH TREE-BORNE OIL PRESERVATIVES”

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Abstract

Bamboo species used mainly for mechanical and physical durability are namely *Dendrocalamus stocksii*, *Dendrocalamus strictus* and *Bambusa balcooa*. The shrinkage of bamboo determines the structural stability and moisture-related behaviour of bamboo. The present investigation was conducted to evaluate the percentage shrinkage of bamboo specimens, along diameter, wall thickness and length of bamboo. The experiment was designed on Factorial Randomized Block Design (FRBD) with three replications. The treatment included boiling hot water treatment at 160° C for 2 hours followed by surface application of Tree-Borne Oils namely, Karanj Oil, Neem Oil and Mahua Oil; and control specimens without oil or heat treatment for comparison.

Observations were recorded on the first day and at the 60th day of treatment. The specimens were kept in ideal air-drying condition. The specimens had increasing trend of shrinkage along length followed by diameter and lastly wall thickness. The result revealed that *D. Stocksii* exhibited favorable shrinkage behaviour and karanj oil had maximum preservation impact.

Key words: Bamboo, Shrinkage, Tree-Borne Oil.

Introduction

Bamboo is increasingly recognized as a sustainable natural resource due to its rapid growth, high strength-to-weight ratio, and versatile applications in construction, furniture, and engineered composites (Sharma et al., 2015). As a lignocellulosic material, bamboo is hygroscopic and therefore undergoes dimensional changes in response to fluctuations in moisture content. These changes manifest primarily as shrinkage and swelling, which directly affect its dimensional stability, mechanical performance, and long-term service life (Malanit et al., 2008).

Unlike wood, bamboo exhibits a complex anisotropic shrinkage pattern arising from its hollow culm structure, gradient fiber distribution, and variation in wall thickness across its height. Shrinkage occurs in three principal directions: longitudinal (along the length), radial (across the wall thickness), and tangential (across the diameter). While longitudinal shrinkage is generally minimal, radial and tangential shrinkage can be substantial, often leading to cracking, splitting, or warping during drying and service (Jain et al., 2015). Understanding these directional shrinkage behaviors is therefore critical for optimizing bamboo's processing, preservation, and structural applications.

Among the numerous bamboo species in South and Southeast Asia, *Dendrocalamus stocksii*, *Dendrocalamus strictus*, and *Bambusa balcooa* hold particular importance due to their strength, durability, and widespread use in scaffolding, housing, and handicrafts. However, despite their economic and ecological relevance, comparative studies on their shrinkage characteristics remain scarce. Recent investigations have indicated that *D. stocksii* exhibits higher shrinkage along wall

thickness compared to diameter and length (Jain et al., 2015), while *B. balcooa* demonstrates improved dimensional stability following chemical treatment (Borthakur & Gogoi, 2009). Meanwhile, *D. strictus*, widely used in structural applications, presents unique challenges of dimensional stability under environmental stresses (Sharma et al., 2015).

This study aims to systematically evaluate and compare the shrinkage behavior of *D. stocksii*, *D. strictus*, and *B. balcooa* in longitudinal, radial, and tangential directions. By quantifying their shrinkage responses, the research seeks to advance species-specific insights into bamboo's anisotropic behaviour and contribute to improved utilization strategies in engineered and structural applications.

Materials and Methods

The experiment was carried out during 2024-25 at AICRP on Agroforestry, C.O.A., Nagpur, Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth Akola. The experiment design was Factorial Randomized Block Design (FRBD) with three replications (R1,R2,R3). Three species namely, *D. stocksii*, *D. strictus* and *B. balcooa* were used. Specimens were obtained from the 5th internode of bamboo poles, and was cut into 100mm internode. These bamboo specimens were then segregated accordingly and were heat treated in boiling hot water for 2 hours at 160° C (Hao et al. 2021). Simultaneously after treatment, specimens were quenched into normal water to facilitate sap removal. After sap removal, specimens were applied three tree-borne oils namely, karanj oil, neem oil and mahua oil, using paintbrush, for oil absorption. These specimens were air dried in shade for 60 days to observe its shrinkage characteristics.

Table No.1. Treatment Details

TREATMENTS	BAMBOO SPECIES + OIL PRESERVATIVES
S ₁ T ₁	Control stocksii
S ₁ T ₂	<i>Dendrocalamus stocksii</i> + Karanj Oil
S ₁ T ₃	<i>Dendrocalamus stocksii</i> + Neem Oil
S ₁ T ₄	<i>Dendrocalamus stocksii</i> + Mahua Oil
S ₂ T ₁	Control strictus
S ₂ T ₂	<i>Dendrocalamus strictus</i> + Karanj Oil
S ₂ T ₃	<i>Dendrocalamus strictus</i> + Neem Oil
S ₂ T ₄	<i>Dendrocalamus strictus</i> + Mahua Oil
S ₃ T ₁	Control balcooa

S ₃ T ₂	<i>Bambusa balcooa</i> + Karanj Oil
S ₃ T ₃	<i>Bambusa balcooa</i> + Neem Oil
S ₃ T ₄	<i>Bambusa balcooa</i> + Mahua Oil

The shrinkage test was conducted to evaluate the dimensional stability of bamboo during moisture loss. Specimens were measured in both green (fresh) and oven-dried conditions using a digital caliper. The percentage of shrinkage along diameter, along wall thickness and along length was calculated using:

$$\text{Shrinkage along diameter, percent} = \frac{D_i - D_f}{D_i} \times 100 \text{ (IS 6874: 2008)}$$

$$\text{Shrinkage along wall thickness, percent} = \frac{t_i - t_f}{t_i} \times 100 \text{ (IS 6874: 2008)}$$

$$\text{Shrinkage along length, percent} = \frac{l_i - l_f}{l_i} \times 100 \text{ (IS 6874: 2008)}$$

Where,

D_i, t_i, l_i = initial dimensions of outer diameter, wall thickness and length, respectively, in mm and

D_f, t_f, l_f = final dimensions of outer diameter, wall thickness and length, respectively, in mm.

The observation was recorded on the 60th day of specimen treatment. The calculation was referred from Bureau of Indian Standards code (IS 6874 : 2008).

Result and Discussion

Table 2. Interaction effect of oil preservative treatment on the shrinkage along diameter of bamboo species

Sr. No.	Bamboo Species (Factor A)	Diameter shrinkage per cent (%)				
		Oil Preservatives Treatment (Factor B)				
		T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄	MEAN
1	S ₁ - <i>D. stocksii</i>	1.34	0.17	0.22	0.18	0.48
2	S ₂ - <i>D. strictus</i>	0.47	0.52	0.40	0.35	0.43
3	S ₃ - <i>B. balcooa</i>	1.10	0.24	0.17	0.07	0.39
	MEAN	0.97	0.31	0.26	0.20	0.43
		A		B		A X B
	SE(m)	0.017		0.019		0.034
	SE(d)	0.024		0.027		0.048
	CD @ 5%	0.049		0.057		0.099
	F Test ±	Sig		Sig		Sig
	CV	13.568				

Of the species evaluated, *D. stocksii* exhibited the highest mean shrinkage (0.48%), indicating the poorest dimensional stability, followed by *D. strictus* (0.43%). *B. balcooa* demonstrated the greatest stability with the lowest mean shrinkage (0.39%). Among treatments, the untreated control (T₁) resulted in the highest shrinkage (0.97%), confirming the inherent instability of untreated bamboo. Mahua oil (T₄) was the most effective treatment, yielding the lowest mean shrinkage (0.20%). Neem oil (T₃) and karanj oil (T₂) produced intermediate results with 0.26% and 0.31% shrinkage, respectively. These results establish that oil treatments, particularly mahua oil, significantly improve the dimensional stability of bamboo.

Similar results were found in a study by, Gomes et al., (2021) revealing, second highest shrinkage in diameter shrinkage also known

as tangential shrinkage. The bamboo specimens of centre and basal region have seen 3.98% and 4.96% dimensional variation-shrinkage as compared to radial and axial shrinkage of similar bamboo poles at similar elevation (centre and base). Ramful et al. (2021) stated, thermal modification showed shrinkage in radial & tangential directions are way greater than longitudinal direction. Explained via orthotropic nature and chemical changes in cellulose/hemicellulose. Anokye et al. (2014), showed radial shrinkage is greater than tangential shrinkage followed by longitudinal shrinkage. Reported a small radial-to-tangential ratio (1.15:1), explaining bamboo's relatively high dimensional stability.

Table 3. Interaction effect of oil preservative treatment on the shrinkage along wall thickness of bamboo species

Sr. No.	Bamboo Species (Factor A)	Wall thickness shrinkage per cent (%)				
		Oil preservatives (Factor B)				
		T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄	MEAN
1	S ₁ - <i>D. stocksii</i>	1.02	0.94	0.39	0.16	0.63
2	S ₂ - <i>D. strictus</i>	1.79	0.73	0.39	0.14	0.76
3	S ₃ - <i>B. balcooa</i>	2.08	0.55	0.28	0.10	0.75
	MEAN	1.63	0.74	0.35	0.13	0.71
		A		B		A X B
	SE(m)	0.020		0.023		0.040
	SE(d)	0.028		0.033		0.057
	CD @ 5%	0.059		0.069		0.119
	F Test ±	Sig		Sig		Sig
	CV	9.897				

Fig. 1. Effect of Oil Treatment on Diameter Shrinkage of Bamboo

Of the species examined, *Dendrocalamus strictus* exhibited the highest mean shrinkage (0.76%), followed closely by *Bambusa balcooa* (0.75%), while *Dendrocalamus stocksii* demonstrated the greatest dimensional stability with the lowest mean shrinkage (0.63%). Across treatments, the untreated control (T_1) resulted in the most severe shrinkage (1.63%), underscoring the inherent structural instability of untreated bamboo. Mahua oil (T_4) was the most effective preservative, drastically reducing the mean shrinkage to 0.13%. Neem oil (T_3) and karanj oil (T_2) provided intermediate stabilization, with shrinkage values of 0.35% and 0.74%, respectively.

A significant species-treatment interaction was observed. The most pronounced shrinkage occurred in untreated *B. balcooa* (2.08%), whereas the same species treated with mahua oil achieved the lowest recorded value (0.10%), demonstrating the treatment's exceptional efficacy in enhancing dimensional stability.

These results are consistent with earlier studies showing that oil heat treatments, particularly with viscous oils, enhance dimensional stability by filling microvoids in the parenchyma and vascular bundles, reducing moisture exchange and associated structural shrinkage (Yuan *et al.*, 2020). Similar reductions in wall contraction following oil heat treatment have been documented in *Gigantochloa scortechinii* using crude palm oil, where lignocellulosic stabilization limited post-treatment shrinkage (Salim *et al.*, 2010). Collectively, these findings demonstrate that both anatomical structure and the physical properties of the oil preservative, particularly viscosity and adhesion, play a decisive role in controlling wall thickness shrinkage, with mahua oil showing the highest efficacy across species.

Table 4. Interaction effect of oil preservative treatment on the shrinkage along length of bamboo species

Sr. No.	Bamboo Species (Factor A)	Along Length Shrinkage Percentage (%)				
		Oil Preservatives Treatment (Factor B)				
		T_1	T_2	T_3	T_4	MEAN
1	$S_1 - D. stocksii$	0.03	0.06	0.04	0.02	0.04
2	$S_2 - D. strictus$	0.01	0.06	0.05	0.02	0.03
3	$S_3 - B. balcooa$	0.09	0.08	0.06	0.01	0.06
	MEAN	0.05	0.06	0.05	0.01	0.04
		A		B	A X B	
	SE(m)	0.0002861		0.0003304	0.0005722	
	SE(d)	0.0004046		0.0004672	0.0008092	
	CD @ 5%	0.0008391		0.0009690	0.0016783	
	F Test ±	Sig		Sig	Sig	
	CV	2.272				

Longitudinal shrinkage values were minimal across all species and treatments, consistent with the inherent stability imparted by the parallel orientation of bamboo fibers. Among species, *Bambusa balcooa* exhibited the highest mean shrinkage (0.06%), while *Dendrocalamus strictus* showed the lowest (0.03%). Mahua oil (T_4) was the most effective treatment, reducing shrinkage to a mean of 0.01%. In contrast, karanj oil (T_2) resulted in the highest treatment mean (0.06%) and even increased shrinkage above control levels in *B. balcooa* and *D. stocksii*. This anomalous effect suggests limited longitudinal oil penetration or suboptimal fiber-oil interactions, diverging from its performance in other shrinkage dimensions. The most significant improvement was observed in *B. balcooa* treated with mahua oil, which reduced shrinkage by 88.9% compared to the untreated control. These results align with previous research establishing that longitudinal shrinkage in bamboo is inherently low, often below 0.1%, due to the axial alignment of vascular bundles and fibers (Liese and Köhl, 2015). Yuan *et al.* (2020) reported that tung oil treatment of *Phyllostachys pubescens* at 100 °C reduced radial and tangential shrinkage by up to 40%, but produced negligible (<0.1%) changes longitudinally, underscoring the minimal responsiveness of this dimension. Li *et al.* (2022) similarly observed that hot oil treatment of bamboo scrimber reduced tangential shrinkage from 3.65% to 1.52% and radial shrinkage from 4.29% to 1.88%, while longitudinal shrinkage remained consistently below 0.05% regardless of treatment, indicating that oil effects in this direction are subtle but measurable.

Fig. 2. Effect of Oil Treatment on Wall Thickness Shrinkage of Bamboo

Fig. 3. Effect of Oil Treatment on Longitudinal Shrinkage of Bamboo

Conclusion

Shrinkage properties varied significantly among species and treatments across all three measured dimensions, with *D. stocksii* generally exhibiting favourable shrinkage characteristics. The shrinkage behaviour improvements across diameter, wall thickness and length dimensions indicate enhanced dimensional stability, which is crucial for construction applications.

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